

Women Entrepreneurship: Culture and Norms - An Indian Perspective

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Abstract

An entrepreneur is historically assumed to be male despite changing demographics with women comprising more than 50% of world population. Impact of sheer numbers, status and position in society should translate in socio-economic manifestation of the world we live. Women entrepreneurs drive global business environment with economic stability and strength. When compared with global initiatives women entrepreneurs in India get a raw deal with abysmally low funding, support, encouragement and initiatives. Can women bring business enterprise change; entrepreneurial drive? Such intensity mirrors culture, norms and employee motivation. India ranks at dismal 70th position amongst 77 nations on participation of women in entrepreneurial roles. Can this change? Yes/ No; India needs to witness increase in participation and initiatives to strengthen women entrepreneurs by transcending barriers, creating new ventures, services and products; organizational adaptability within the myths and realities of culture and norms; shift in culture and norms redefining stereotyping. Present exploratory study aims to assess Indian perspective of women in entrepreneurship within the domain of culture and norms and propose a model for organizations to assess their strength on women entrepreneurship. Themes identified are; 2.2 Organization, 2.0 Organization, 1.9 Organization and 1.0 Organization.

Keywords: Women entrepreneurs, Entrepreneurial intensity and drive, Culture, Norms

1. Introduction

C. P. Kothawale cites entrepreneur is derived from French word *entreprendre*; to undertake. One of the many perspectives of entrepreneur is a person executing the ability to combine capital and labour for production (Kothawale, 2015) and women cannot do entrepreneurship! Entrepreneurs lay foundation for innovation, economic growth and job creation. Do men and women get equal opportunity to become entrepreneurs? In comparison to men, women entrepreneurs in India get a raw deal despite numbers and changing personal dynamics; higher confidence, education, skills, knowledge, abilities and competence. While women entrepreneurship world over is established with growth and development of women and nations they represent, what needs to change in India; policies, mindset, practices and/ or culture and norms? There is a need to look around, reinvent, focus and invest in supporting and encouraging women in entrepreneurship for global growth. Women entrepreneurship is *the way forward*; inclusive and sustainable development.

2. Review of Literature

An entrepreneur is historically assumed to be male.³ Robert Ronstand cites entrepreneurship as a dynamic process of creating incremental wealth.⁴ Schumpeter describes entrepreneurship as turning dreams into reality.⁵ Kothawale defines women entrepreneurship as business enterprise managed by women with a share capital of more than 51%. Fisher et.al suggest larger cross section of women see themselves as feminists undertaking unconventional roles in starting business enterprise by stepping outside of traditionally defined roles (Brush, 1992; Fisher, 1993). R C Yadav opines Indian organizations have been primarily male-dominated with women accounting for only 20% workforce.⁶ International Labour Organization ranks India at 121 out of 131 countries in women labour force participation. In this, apart from other factors culture and norms dictate women to be confined to home doing family chores. Statistics are shocking; while participation of men is high women participation has been on the decline. As per National Sample Survey Organization women participation in India has dropped from 40% to 22.8% over the last decade (Yadav, 2015).

2.1 Women in Entrepreneurship

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³ www.ukessays.com > Essays > Sociology

⁴ ksu.edu.sa/.../ENTREPRENEURSHIP/.../R_History_of_Entrep_Ch2_rese...

⁵ www.investopedia.com/terms/j/joseph-schumpeter.asp

⁶ www.censusindia.gov.in/2011-common/census_2011.html

Lubna Kably shares India ranks at 70th position in a survey of 77 countries for participation of women in entrepreneurship (Kably, 2015). Support and encouragement for women entrepreneurship world over is the key to growth and development of women and nations they represent, however, women in India are denied general opening up of horizon in exposure and experience; know-how, assistance, access to information, programs and training. Women represent minority of entrepreneurs and possibility of becoming more successful and visible eludes communities (Shah, 2015).

Figure 1: Women entrepreneurship index 2015⁷

Global comparison by world economic forum 2014 reflects poorly on women participation as India's position appears at 124 amongst 136 nations and BRICS nation rank higher than India. UN gender statistics brings out a decline in women participation in India. Catalyst cites women in India hold less than 5% board seats lower than BRICS countries despite law mandating all companies listed on SEBI to have at least one woman board member (Madhok, 2014).

Figure 2: Comparison of workforce participation: men v/s women⁸

Zoya Khan cites skewed percentage exists on participation of women against men. Rural sector comprises major chunk of unorganized labour force; lack of education, skill and training compared to urban counterparts. Labour force and workforce percentage participation rates also stand skewed.

Figure 3: Participation of women in unorganized sector⁹

Discrimination remains contentious and an ever present issue for women in entrepreneurship. Societal underestimation and structure of unorganized sector makes it a non-conducive work environment for women. Managing household work and complementing family income makes the issue of statistically measuring a women's work complex task. Socio-cultural norms further inhibit already shrunk sphere lowering women participation in conventional sense (Khan, 2013).

Neelam opines women in India chose micro enterprises as it allows them to stay in control of business and personal lives, integrate career roles and family; quality of life.¹⁰ Dil Pazir and Shokit Hussian opine degree of recognition and strategic support provided to women in micro, small and medium sector is inadequate. Despite the fact that the promotion of women entrepreneurs is a prerequisite for overall economic growth and alleviation of poverty, women entrepreneurs have not been provided with constructive assistance from

⁷ thegedi.org/research/women-entrepreneurship-index/

⁸ qz.com/.../India's-record-in-women's-participation-in-the-workforce-is-de...

⁹ Report on Conditions of Work and Promotion of Livelihoods in the Unorganized Sector (Arjun SenGupta Committee Report) by National Commission for Enterprises in the Unorganized Sector- NCEUS, 2007

¹⁰ www.naaree.com/top-successful-women-entrepreneurs-india/

government w.r.t recognition, access to finance and skills. In India MSME sector provides livelihood to 49% of employed women, however, strategic support from the government has been minimal. On the contrary this area has considerably improved in Bangladesh, Singapore, Japan, China, South Korea, Taiwan and Malaysia. Success is attributed to support, financial aid, policies, respect for basic rights and needs of women. In India women depend on MSMEs as a source of livelihood essentially because government fails to meet survival and entrepreneurial aspirations. 2005, 2003 and 2002 survey by World Bank and World Trade Organization indicate women entrepreneurs in India can institute new business and enterprises at a rate twice as fast as men but find it harder to grow to the next level (Dil Pazir, 2012). With this the unorganized sector accounts for almost 90% of total work force in India and in this women constitute only 1/3rd.¹¹

This leads to formulation of following Proposition:

Proposition 1: *Women entrepreneurs in India are passive players. Given the abilities and numbers, organizations need to focus on women entrepreneurs translating individual success into social, economic, business and national success.*

2.2 Culture, Norms and women entrepreneurship

Hayton regards culture as key variable in understanding entrepreneurial perspective; integral – way of life. Culture lends norms; shared beliefs giving power to influence individual behaviors, how people should or should not behave and act inclusive of gender roles (Hayton, 2002). Kottak suggests culture cascades into strong propositions; beliefs - norms. Mueller and Thomas bring out initiative, support and encouragement largely depends on culture and norms; societal and organizational factors prevailing in society/ organization we live in. Culture and norms thus restrict and/ or promote women in entrepreneurship (Stephen Mueller, 2001). Norms; evolve from culture - established standards of conformed behaviour, powerful prescriptions. With rigid views on gender roles Indian culture reinforces restricting women to domestic and family work preventing independent creative and innovative action for evolving as entrepreneur; the norm.¹² Shah cites United Nations Conference on Trade and Development 2013 brings out women entrepreneurs in India are considered to have relatively lesser experience in handling external business contacts for innovation due difficulty in dealing with complexity and work life integration challenges. Gender gap index 2015 indicates India at 114th rank among 145 countries regressing in almost all sectors; decline not only relative to its international peers but also in absolute terms widening the gap with persistent wage inequalities; strong glass ceiling persists.

2.3 Societal Culture and Norms

There is no society in the world where more women on an average are leading men. Gender differences are shaped by culture (Adeleke, 2003). Societal culture is deep in values, attitudes, norms, practices, stratifications and related ways of society. In this women choosing entrepreneurship the non-traditional career is influenced by societal disruptions.¹³ Despite constitutional rights for gender equality and equal opportunity in India different standards of behaviour for men and women extend into society and work environment. Rural areas at large view participation of women outside home as an inappropriate virtue of woman

(L Dubey, 1990). Nelasco opines Indian culture masks leadership potential of women.¹⁴ Societal culture and norms through mind set, practice and male dominance result in lack of exposure of outside world to women. Working within a confined ecosystem Indian women even though capable and aspiring remain dependent on men; are deprived of entrepreneurship (Shah H. , 2012).

2.4 Organizational Culture and Norms

¹¹ sahaas.blogspot.com/2011/.../employment-in-organised-sector-how_22.h...

¹² https://www.unido.org/.../Women.../Brochure_low_resolution.pdf

¹³ <https://www.questia.com/.../on-the-theory-of-social-change-how-economy...>

¹⁴ iosrjournals.org/iosr-jbm/papers/ies-mcrrc-ibrc/volume-3/RC-34.pdf

Neely et.al identified factors at different levels with respect to organizational culture impacting women in entrepreneurship; support, innovation, flexibility, culture, adaptability, autonomy, risk taking, entrepreneurial edge, communication, decision making, motivation, recognition, opportunity, tolerance to ambiguity, ownership, behaviour, commitment, trust, initiative and strategic thinking. Innovative companies have a strong culture; clear sense of purpose, business philosophy, strategy and quality management practices (Neely, 2001). Edgar Schein posits leadership is critical to creating organizational culture and vice versa (Schein, 1992). Senge et.al opine culture holds organizations and transforms into newer competitive state; profound impact on organizations entrepreneurial capability. Motivation and entrepreneurship in organizations go together and directly reflect on the norms and culture (Senge, 2001). Slavica Singer et.al share key to organizational entrepreneurial ability is being pro-active, taking risk and being innovative (Singer, 2014).

Macro environment manifests social, cultural, political and economic effects due policies and practices. Culture and norms dictate women’s propensity for pursuing new ventures. Micro dictates through behaviour, attitude and motivation. Women in India therefore have to somewhat contend to culture and norms unfavourable and restrictive w.r.t entrepreneurship. A reflection of macro and micro environment variables is as shown in figure.

Figure 4: Organizational culture driving norms and impacting women in entrepreneurship¹⁵

Gunter Faltn identified key drivers for an entrepreneurial organizational culture to break-in and shudder existing market symmetry through *efficient allocation of resources, creative destruction, feeling the mission, driving passion to create something new/ different, build something out of nothing, connect with goals in the sense of feeling the journey and outcome all through and that entrepreneurial motivation comes from patience and perseverance; more than money* (Faltn, 2001). At the macro level globalization, modernization and technology shape the role of women in entrepreneurship. In this although the notion on women has changed in some countries, in India women are still considered for familial duties. Women entrepreneurs are influenced by both pull and push factors. Pull factors; aspirations for autonomy and independence, personal satisfaction and achievement, challenge, gender stereotypes, gap in the market and Push factors; dissatisfaction with the labour market, need for greater income, unemployment, desire for a better life or higher earnings, financial incentive and motivation from government/ schemes for assistance, attraction of high profit margins.

2.5 Barriers to women in entrepreneurship

Women in entrepreneurship are marked with leadership, confidence and managerial skills for accessing new markets. Schaefer suggests entrepreneurship offers women challenges of learning how to effectively operate activities of entrepreneurial business and simultaneously attempt to meet all expectations part of entrepreneurship.¹⁶ Anyanwu and Ayogu opine rigid culture and norms are thrust upon on women along with overbearing influence of a male dominated society (Ayogu, 2013). Hafizullah et.al highlighted cultural male dominance stalls women entrepreneur’s w.r.t mobility, business participation and market interactions. Women entrepreneurs in India face traditional and contemporary environments; traditional due socio cultural and norms and contemporary due structure, policies and institutional mechanism (Hafizullah, 2012). Kothawale brings out some of the concerns diluting women entrepreneurs in India are; low confidence, non availability of finance, socio cultural practices, norms, lack of managerial skills, competition, lack of knowledge, education, skills, lower risk taking ability and mobility constraints. United Nations Industrial

¹⁵ <https://books.google.co.in/books?isbn=1136496084>

¹⁶ shodhganga.inflibnet.ac.in:8080/jspui/bitstream/.../6/chapter%203.pdf

Development Organization study on barriers to women in entrepreneurship identifies greater influence of traditional and internal set factors; culture and norms. Entrepreneurship is seen as an inappropriate career choice for women in India. Researchers have also identified difficulty in acquiring entrepreneurial skills and lack of confidence as primary concerns with respect to women entrepreneurship.¹⁷ Arvinda opines inability to expand enterprise; nurture skills, confidence, knowledge, skills, taking risk, socio cultural practices, societal support and work life integration are some of the challenges for women in India (Arvinda, 2001). Steve Radelet brings out key challenges to women entrepreneurship in India as; low risk tolerance, business decision making, education, lack of information and network, legal and regulatory framework, culture and social norms.¹⁸ Women in India are perceived with limits in education, guidance and training coupled with technology accessibility and know-how to reach full potential. World Bank report cites low productivity and limited growth sectors are central to subdued women entrepreneurs in developing countries.¹⁹ International Labour Organization report cites 94% women (more than 800 million) in the world capable to strengthen respective national economy are living in developing and emerging economies.²⁰

2.6 Global perspectives on Women Entrepreneurship

Figure 5: Global Gender Gap report 2014

Global Gender Gap Report emphasizes persisting gender gap divides across and within regions. Based on nine years of data 111 countries world has seen only a small improvement in equality for women in workplace. According to the report gender gap for economic participation and opportunity now stands at 60% worldwide. Global studies also indicate; strengthening women entrepreneurs in comparison to men will have direct impact on GDP increase by 34% in some countries and productivity increase by 25%.²¹

Amudha opines women bring in positive energy and work diversity through focus and exploration and Fortune 500 companies have shown increase in profits and business expansion. Women entrepreneurs in Germany, Spain, European Union, Israel, France, Italy, Malaysia, Austria and Belgium translate increase in company income (Amudha, 2015).

Figure 6: World Economic Forum Report²²

WES report on European Network to promote women entrepreneurship indicated an entrepreneurship action plan adopted by Commission in February 2004 with focus on access to finance and networking alongside additional activities as priority at national and regional level. Diane project in Belgium and First National Report on women entrepreneurship in Italy are outstanding initiatives that can be taken as good examples to

¹⁷ www.ripublication.com/gjmbs_spl/gjmbsv3n10_15.pdf

¹⁸ www.cipe.org/.../constraints-to-women-entrepreneurship-in-emerging-e...

¹⁹ www.unwomen.org/en/what-we-do/economic.../facts-and-figures

²⁰ www.ilo.org/empent/areas/womens-entrepreneurship...wed/lang--en/

²¹ unctad.org/en/Pages/DTL/STI_and_ICTs/ICT4D-Women.aspx

²² www.weforum.org/reports

be replicated. Ladies Business School has been operational for 20 years in Finland with micro credit programmes in Spain and Finland. Public and private sector activities promoting women entrepreneurship have been carried out in Austria; networking through events; Business Woman 2004 and Ideas to Business (i2b). Other initiatives include women-business-mentoring-fair in March 2004 in Vienna with the second fair in March 2005 in Graz. With regard to internet activities, in 2004 several new initiatives were launched; Lower-Austrian electronic business platform for women (for e-business) and new internet-platform women2business. Basic aim besides strengthening entrepreneurial activities of women has been creation of new modern viable enterprises, development of innovative projects, new technologies, products and support services enhancing quality and development.²³ WED initiated women entrepreneurship development programme in Norway; 2 phase 5 year capacity training programme for women entrepreneurs in East Africa supported by Norwegian Agency for Development Cooperation (NORAD) in cooperation with women entrepreneur organizations; AWANEA (African Women Agribusiness Network East Africa) and NAWOU (National Association of Women Organizations in Uganda). Training includes women driven companies mainly coming from Uganda, Kenya, Tanzania and Ethiopia.²⁴

Saikou E. Sanyang and Wen-Chi Huang cite women entrepreneurs in Taiwan are as capable as men in running a business.²⁵ Hanna Mizgajska's study suggests education and professional experiences of women in Poland were decisive in prioritizing external and internal factors impacting decisions in entrepreneurship and significant in influencing company growth.²⁶ Milcah Mulu Mutuku in her study on 106 Kenyan women micro entrepreneurs opines renewed interest in female entrepreneurship as policy makers recognize importance of social inclusiveness in economic development. In Kenya, women entrepreneurs have low levels of education; need for business knowledge and skills and finance for business development services, are affected by patriarchal structures; role of husbands. Yet women own growing businesses contributing in creating wealth and employment. 76.9% micro entrepreneurs drive business without prior business skills, 5.5% had training in business before starting businesses, 17.6% learnt business skills from previous employment and an entrepreneurship development curriculum weaved through school syllabus helped entrenching an enterprising culture among women (Mutuku, 2015).

Inter-American bank and multilateral investment fund operate women entrepreneurship banking WEB for incentives. This translates in congruence at highest level akin to initiatives by USAID and World Bank; women leadership in small and medium enterprises through collaborative and innovative interventions in creating best practices.²⁷ Dell launched *pay it forward initiative* expanding opportunities for women entrepreneurs. UN Foundation and Exxon Mobil Foundation released a roadmap for promoting women economic empowerment identifying interventions that increase productivity and earnings for women in diverse country contexts.²⁸ Shift in culture and norms in countries has given women an opportunity to enter mainstream social, economic and business spheres often denied due gender bias and/ or perceptions. World Economic Forum Gender Gap Report cites U.S. has experienced 11 percent growth over last 40 years as a direct result of increased participation of women translating into fiscal benefit of \$3.5 trillion. If barriers to women entrepreneurship were reduced, Gross Domestic Product of Japan would grow 16 percent.²⁹ Challenging, complex and turbulent business world; present and future therefore demands greater adaptability and transformation; change the way we think and operate.

This leads to formulation of following Proposition:

Proposition 2: *Indian culture and norms are changing; a paradigm shift is happening. A shift in culture and norms gives women an opportunity to enter mainstream social, economic and business*

²³ www.atvinnuugaraduneyti.is/media/Acrobat/skyrsla.doc

²⁴ www.virke.no/omvirke/aboutvirke/International-trade/Sider/WED.aspx

²⁵ www.researchgate.net/.../242614193_Small_and_Medium_Enterprise_for_...

²⁶ jml2012.indexpopernicus.com/fulltxt.php?ICID=972344

²⁷ www.gew.co/women

²⁸ www.unescap.org/sites/.../ESCAP-SSWA-Development-Paper_1304_1.p...

²⁹ reports.weforum.org/global-gender-gap-report-2014/

spheres often denied due gender bias and/ or perceptions. Culture and norms need to evolve, support and encourage women entrepreneur's in present day; micro and macro level for personal and organizational success. There is need to examine, identify, create and/ or emulate norms from third world economies/ developed countries for women in entrepreneurship in India.

2.7 Women Entrepreneurship is the way forward

Bonnie Ross Parker identifies key traits for women enduring entrepreneurship; drive, vision, autonomy, intuition, distinctiveness, planner and risk taker (Parker, 2010). Challenges are complex and organizations need to; provide financial support, remove cultural and social barriers, legal barriers, improve accessibility, promote education by extending management education to develop business skills and build networks.³⁰ Organizations willing to take more risks, be more flexible, creative, aggressive and innovative at all levels; individual, organizational and societal to deal uncertainty and challenges will help women move forward in entrepreneurial role with greater intensity (Gibb, 2000).

Jack Zenger and Joseph Folkman identified women scored better than men at work. Women rated higher in more than 90% of study competencies indicating outstanding entrepreneurship and leadership; key traits being initiative and driving results (Folkman, 2012). Pallavi Jha cites while women face challenges in a fast changing business world with entrepreneurship, rejecting women workforce; skills and ability translates in losing more than 50% of talent to prejudice (Jha, 2015).

Figure 7: Performance of women in comparison to men at workplace³¹

FICCI ladies organization (FLO) conducts training, business consultancy, networking and recognition; awareness and development programme for women in entrepreneurship for excellence and prosperity.³² NASSCOM focuses on building gender diverse workforce. IT-BPM, a knowledge-intensive sector and equal opportunity employer has been hiring women over past decade. 8,00,000 women currently working account for over 30 per cent of existing hires and is all set to rise in future.³³ Micro, Small and Medium enterprise development organizations, State Small Industries development corporations, National banks and NGOs are conducting entrepreneurship development programmes for women entrepreneurs. Government schemes for assistance, training-cum-income also exist with Small Industries Development Bank of India implementing special schemes for women entrepreneurs.³⁴ Hina Shah cites women are doing leadership; entrepreneurial development is being recognized as an important and untapped source of economic growth. For women in entrepreneurship MSME is the engine for growth (Shah H. , 2013).

This leads to formulation of following Proposition:

Proposition 3: *In the back drop of challenges due culture and norms women entrepreneur potential when unlocked creates a positive impact across social, financial, professional and economic boundaries.*

3. Methodology

³⁰ www.goldmansachs.com/citizenship/10000women/

³¹ Zenger Folkman Inc. 2011

³² www.ficciflo.com/

³³ www.nasscom.in/women-top

³⁴ smallb.sidbi.in/%20fund-your.../additional.../women-entrepreneurship

This study used exploratory research design and secondary data from articles, papers and reports to understand perspective of culture and norms, concerns and challenges for women in entrepreneurship in an Indian perspective.

4. Rationale

With seven decades of independence Indian women continue to struggle for entrepreneurial freedom. Woman as entrepreneurial resource has not yet been accepted in India. Harnessing women potential with an inclusive approach is critical to sustain economic and national development with transparency. Studies indicate 870 million women entrepreneur contributing at subsistence level are getting ready to emerge as mainstream employees and producers in the next five years.³⁵ Habib concludes women entrepreneurs can emerge from socially marginal groups; based on culture, ethnicity and/ or migrant minority because socio-cultural environment has far-reaching impact on entrepreneurs (Habib, 2005). Marton contends women are no longer confined to an ascribed status and that they have earned respect and recognition outside home working for social, economic and national development resulting in greater social sanction and empowerment; shift in culture and norms is visible (Marton, 1972). Women in entrepreneurship as powerful driver of change can neither be stalled nor ignored; evolve measurable model w.r.t culture, norms and opportunities recognizing women as important and untapped job source and business solution for growth.

5. Discussion and Analysis

Women entrepreneurs contribute in business solutions and are identified as an important source of economic growth and job creation. Women in India are no longer confined to four walls and actively contribute in multiple activities. Starting an enterprise is taking just another step. Culture and norms not only repress quality of life but limit productivity, economic efficiency and growth contrary to good governance on women in entrepreneurship. Status quo is of no good; transformation of women in entrepreneurship will lead to increase in country's GDP by more than a quarter; empowering and investing in women will help drive and promote economic vitality.³⁶ GMI survey data for 6,000 companies in 45 countries indicates slow progress in most countries outside Europe necessitating legal mandates for increasing the number of women entrepreneurs and their representation in the board. While India has seen an increase of 1.3% in the level of women directors since 2011; faster rate of change than in many other countries, it is far from supporting and encouraging women as entrepreneurs.³⁷ Study carried out by Amudha reveals board of a private sector company run by a mix of both professional men and women translated in 4.4% higher return of equity in 2014 in comparison to previous year. Similar company with only men on board translated in return of equity increased by only 1.8% during the same period (Amudha, 2015). Women have embraced technology creating marketing channels, customer information that can improve business process efficiency; 81% of women in India use technology for business solutions.³⁸ Dileepkumar and Khanka cite higher education, economic liberalization, initiative, support and encouragement from nongovernmental organizations and some self-help groups has brought about an upsurge of women entrepreneurs in India. In a paradigm shift India has witnessed some of the successful women entrepreneurs; effort and journey needs to be increased and sustained not only for women from middle and lower middle classes but also rural areas (Dileepkumar, 2006).

³⁵ www.unfoundation.org/blog/female-entrepreneurs.html

³⁶ http://www.strategyand.pwc.com/media/file/Strategyand_2012-Empowering-the-Third-Billion_Briefing-Deck.pdf

³⁷ https://www.boarddiversity.ca/sites/.../GMIRatings_WOB_042013.pdf

³⁸ https://www.kpmg.com/.../The_Cloud_Changing_the_Business_Ecosyste...

Women entrepreneurship clearly is *the way forward*. Notion and legacy of leaders in innovative organizations to articulate, share vision motivate people and have clarity of focus and purpose needs to expand and extend to women. What is empowerment for women if it means permanent dependency on others? Empowerment can come only through capability and capacity building and independence. Women entrepreneurs are game changers.³⁹

Figure 8: Global women entrepreneur environment⁴⁰

Vanderburgh cites women in emerging markets plough back 90% of additional income into human resources; translating in enhanced national strength against 30% to 40% for men (Vanderbrug, 2013). Worldwide efforts to empower women entrepreneurs become business owners are happening world over and closing the gender gap in India requires more efforts; clustering of services to bring in a changed perspective on women entrepreneurship. Present age is marked with rising education levels, growing customer sophistication, change, breaking barriers, creativity and innovation and reduced gender gaps in creating a coherent entrepreneurial ecosystem. There is a need to encourage, support and evolve a culture by way of appreciative beliefs, sustainable economy, ground real policies and norms will create an enabling environment for women entrepreneurship.⁴¹ Breaking the glass ceiling with shift in culture, norms for change needs validation, legal mandate and practice in organized and un-organized sectors through – *Awareness and learning*; reaching out to women in all areas with transparency bringing trust and confidence in women to take the next step. *Development of entrepreneurial attitude*; women need to break out of the traditional mould and venture out. Indian Institute of Entrepreneurship Guwahati and National Institute of Entrepreneurship and Small Business Development, New Delhi have started special programmes promoting women entrepreneurship. Initiatives by NABARD by way of credit flow, expansion and diversification, transfer of technology, communication and strengthening potential linked with planning foster women entrepreneurship. *Accessibility to financial support*; financial support through central women entrepreneur fund for easy credit, loans and policies; economic empowerment for starting business enterprise will promote women entrepreneurs. *Attribution Augmenting*; attribution augmenting enhances ratings when women become entrepreneur and reduces the potential impact of negative gender stereotype. *Entrepreneurial Motivation*; women entrepreneurial motivation and success will translate career development. *Networking*; teaching benefits of networking for access to resources. *Revisiting policies*; creating women business to business centers, upgrading policies, transparency, training with funding and creating ground real projects. *Removal of biases and barriers*; women need to be motivated to avail entrepreneurial benefits, elevating to higher levels with a shift in culture and norms, sharing of information for informed decision making and elimination of norms propagating negative attitude towards women. *Encouraging partnership and competition*; bringing in collaborative strength, competitive environment along with challenge, incentives and recognition. *Evolving best practices*; creating and sharing best practices for collective growth, development and building a women entrepreneur value chain.

6. The Future

Women entrepreneurs in India akin to other parts of world have the potential. 21st century leadership skills; vision, taking risks, creating culture, inspiration and motivation, trust, ownership, communication and collaboration are strongly associated with women in entrepreneurship. Women entrepreneur potential when unlocked creates a positive impact across social, financial and economic boundaries. There is a need for stronger commitment and systemic execution. 19th November as women entrepreneurship day demands concrete plans and programmes in support of women entrepreneurs in every continent.

³⁹ www.i-open.org/.../women-entrepreneurs-in-developing-nations-growth-

⁴⁰ womenentrepreneursgrowglobal.org/

⁴¹ https://books.google.co.in/books?isbn=1409498239

A proposed model to enable organizations assess current posture and road ahead w.r.t macro and micro environment is shown in figure. Building a think tank of Indian women leaders should be the defining goal. Macro and micro environment need to evolve and merge on a creative platform to bring women entrepreneurship to forefront; ripple is created and set in motion with a progressive attitude.

Figure 9: Proposed model for organizational assessment w.r.t women entrepreneurship

Themes defining an organizations status/ version are; **2.2 organization**; evolving macro and micro environment brings shift in culture, norms, policies, behaviour and motivation with higher opportunities for women in entrepreneurship through good policies, programmes supported by networking, funding, initiative, encouragement and training. **2.0 organization**; evolving macro environment and rigid micro environment for women in entrepreneurship indicates need to open up micro environment through leadership, initiative, personal development, motivation, higher risk taking, encouragement fostering entrepreneurial behaviour. **1.9 organization**; rigid macro environment and evolving micro environment indicates absence of women participation due imposition of restrictions due culture and norms confining women to home. There is need for leadership to take the next step bring in change of mind set and increased awareness and bring equality - change else be extinct. **1.0 organization**; rigid macro and micro environment indicates rigid culture, norms, policies and unwillingness to change leading to minimal opportunities for women in entrepreneurship thus confining them to familial duties. Organization needs to open up to present and future, provide entrepreneurial opportunities to women through policies, programmes and funding before they become extinct.

7. Limitations and Scope for future research

Women entrepreneurship w.r.t culture and norms has a wider extant and generalization can be strengthened by further study in small and large companies, for-profit/ non-profit sectors with respect to perception and approaches. Qualitative research with comparative analysis on male entrepreneurs and factors brought out at different organizational levels in cultivating culture both societal and organizational could bring in more objectivity and stronger generalization to qualify findings and formulate best practices for encouraging and supporting women in entrepreneurship.

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